

THE FATIGUE PROPERTIES OF A 6061 ALUMINUM MATRIX
REINFORCED WITH CROSS-PLIED BORON FIBERS

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Fatigue tests have been carried out on 6061 aluminum reinforced with boron fibers. Completely reversed tension-compression cycles ($R=-1$) were applied using a hydraulic servocontrolled machine operating at 10-30 Hz. Unnotched and center notched specimens were prepared from material having the fibers oriented parallel and perpendicular to the load axis and from a balanced material having additional fibers oriented in the $+45^\circ$ directions. Thirteen layers of boron fibers having a diameter of 5.6×10^{-3} ins were used to form 12 in x 12 in panels nominally 0.1 in thick containing approximately 47 v/o of reinforcement. Individual specimens, 4 in x 1 in, were cut from each panel using electric discharge machining.